

THE ROLE OF MELATONIN IN THE PATHOGENESIS AND TREATMENT OF POLYCYSTIC OVARY SYNDROME

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Annotation

Polycystic ovary syndrome is one of the most common endocrine diseases in women of reproductive age, a condition characterized by hormonal imbalance, insulin resistance, inflammation, sleep and mood disorders. Recent studies have shown that the level of melatonin in follicular fluid is reduced in women with polycystic ovary syndrome, and in most cases their sleep quality is impaired.

Objectives

To study and evaluate the effect of melatonin on hormonal balance, metabolic and reproductive functions in women with polycystic ovary syndrome and to consider its potential as an additional therapeutic agent in the treatment process.

Main part

1. Let's consider the mechanism of action of melatonin:

- Regulation of circadian rhythms: melatonin is synthesized in the pineal gland and regulates biological rhythms, including the sleep-wake cycle.
- Antioxidant effect: Melatonin neutralizes free radicals, reduces oxidative stress for the body, and these effects play a key role in the pathogenesis of polycystic ovary syndrome.
- Regulation of hormonal activity: Melatonin affects the secretion of gonadotropins and sex hormones and enhances aromatase activity, and at the same time regulates the level of estrogen.

2. Clinical significance of melatonin in the course and therapeutic direction of polycystic ovary syndrome:

- Hormonal balance: Adding melatonin to the treatment plan of women with polycystic ovary syndrome leads to normalization of testosterone and estrogen levels and an improvement in the FSG / LG ratio
- Improvement of oocyte and embryo quality: Melatonin can improve the quality of oocytes and embryos in women with polycystic ovary syndrome, which can be of great importance in pregnancy planning.
- Reducing the effects of oxidative reactions: The antioxidant activity of melatonin can help reduce the levels of oxidative factors such as MDA and hs-CRP.

- Improving sleep and mood: Melatonin can improve sleep quality and reduce symptoms of depression and anxiety in women with this syndrome.

3. How to dose and ensure safety of melatonin.

Safety of use: Melatonin is usually well tolerated by the body when used in the short term.

Dosage: The recommended dose of melatonin is 5-10 mg per day, the most optimal time is 30-60 minutes before bedtime.

Contraindications: It is not recommended to use during pregnancy, breastfeeding, autoimmune diseases and while taking medications that affect melatonin levels.

4. Prospects for the use of melatonin in the treatment of polycystic ovary syndrome

Complementary therapy: Adding melatonin to the treatment plan as a treatment for polycystic ovary syndrome may be as effective as metformin and inositol in reducing excess body weight and insulin resistance, which can occur in more than 80% of women with this syndrome.

Need for further scientific and medical research: Further clinical studies are needed to confirm the efficacy and safety of long-term use of melatonin in the treatment of polycystic ovary syndrome.

Conclusion

In short, melatonin has a multifaceted effect, including antioxidant activity, hormonal regulation, and improving sleep quality. Its use in the treatment of polycystic ovary syndrome may be promising, but further research is needed to optimize the dosage and duration of use.

List of used literature:

1. ICH GCP > реестр клинических исследований США “Эффекты мелатонина у женщин с СПКЯ”
2. “Не только гормон сна. Мелатонин и женские болезни” 21 марта 2024 Екатерина Творогова
3. Медицинский журнал RusMed Сеченовский Университет “Анализ информативности определения мелатонина при синдроме поликистозных яичников”

